

N₄O₂ Ligand with Some Complexes: Synthesis, Characterization and Biological Study

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ABSTRACT: Poly dentate amide ligand type N₄O₂ was prepared by react one mole from tri ethylene tetra amine (TETA) and two moles from the amino acid (tyrosine). the chelate Complexes were prepared from the action between the di valance chloride salts for the first row transition metal ions (Cu⁺², Ni⁺², Co⁺² and Fe⁺²) respectively and free ligand, metal: ligand ratio (M: L) were (1: 1), prepared ligand and its complexes were characterized in solid state by (FT-IR, UV-Vis., ¹HNMR and metal, elemental analysis C.H.N.) spectroscopies techniques, addition to the magnetic susceptibility and molar conductivity for the complexes. these techniques show octahedral structure, SP³d² hybridization and para- magnetic state, in addition non- electrolyte property for all prepared chelate complexes, as well as the biological study to all compounds using gram positive G(+) (*Staph.aureus*) bacteria and gram negative G(-) (*E.Coli*) bacteria in concentration (500) ppm identified that some of these compounds were sensitive towards bacteria.

KEYWORDS: tyrosine TETA, Amide ligand, Complexes, biological study.

I. INTRODUCTION

Coordination compounds have big role in chemistry. it known as complexes, which have central ion or atom (Lewis acid) surrounded by many of ions or molecules could ligands (Lewis base) attached with central atom with coordination bond. ¹ These complexes have huge importance in industry, agriculture, medicine and engineering ², addition on all that, many of them have special importance in biological activity as anti- (bacterial, fungal, tumor) and anti-HIV ³⁻⁵.

Many studies show that compounds used in many reactions as catalyst and reagents because it have donating atoms as oxygen, nitrogen, sulphate and phosphors, so it used in many another applications ⁶⁻⁸, like Radio-pharmacy and as mimics in biological systems ⁹. In the other hand, amides define as a compounds contained active group H₂N-C=O synthesize from carbonyl group -C=O link with primary amine group -NH₂.

Amides divided to two major groups, (aromatic and aliphatic), and all so divided to (primary, secondary, tertiary), because of resonance between π - electrons on carbonyl group and un sheered pair of electrons on nitrogen atom, the aromatic amides activity decreased than aliphatic, Most of them are solid except the simplest one is liquid (form amide), most of them have high fusion degrees. amides prepared by react alcohol or Easters with primary amines, in this study carboxyl group in tyrosine amino acid react with primary multi amine, with H₂O molecule losing ⁹⁻¹³.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

All chemicals were purchased from Fluka, Merck, Himedia, BDH, and Sigma-Aldrich. Melting point were measured by (electro thermal) melting point apparatus Shimadzu FTIR 8400 spectrometer using KBr in the wavelength range 400–4000 cm⁻¹, ¹H-NMR spectra by used Broker-400 MHz –Germany with the solvent DMSO-d⁶. Ultra Violet-Visible spectrum recorded by (UV-1800-SHIMADZU- UV-Spectrophotometer), and electrical Conductivity by Mi-805, Combined meter, pH / EC / TDS /Temperature (Milwaukee).

III. SYNTHESIS OF LIGAND (H₂L)

by adding (0.001 mole, 1.15 ml) from tri ethylene tetra amine to (0.002 mol, 0.262 gm) tyrosine in ice bath (0-5)°C with stirring, we got a white gelatin compound, then add 25 ml of hot methanol (30°C), we notice white participate, filter and wash twice with cold ethanol and acetone [14], after dry give 0.51 gm, 75%, MP: (369-371) °C, formula: C₂₄H₃₆N₆O₄, M.wt: 472.6 gm/ mole, C:61.00, H:7.68, N:17.76 found C:60.61, H:7.64, N: 17.81.

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Fig.. 1. Synthesis of ligand

IV. SYNTHESIS OF COMPLEX

A. Synthesis of [Fe L] Complex

Add (1×10^{-3} mole, 0.2 gm) from $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dissolve in 10ml of ethanol to (0.001 mole, 0.473 g) dissolved H_2L in 10 ml of ethanol with stirring and reflux to $(65-75)^\circ\text{C}$, for three h, notice brown participate, filtered then washed in cold ethanol and acetone, drying participate give 0.43 g, 81.5 %, MP: (dec.386) $^\circ\text{C}$, formula : $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{Fe}$, M.wt : 526.4 gm/mole, C:54.76, H:6.51, N:15.96, O:12.16, Fe:10.61 found C: 54.64, H:6.43, N:15.83, O:12.01, Fe:10.55 .

B. Synthesis of [Co L] Complex

Add (1×10^{-3} mole, 0.24 gm) from $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dissolve in 10ml of ethanol to (0.001 mol, 0.473 g) dissolved H_2L in 10 ml of ethanol with stirring and reflux to $(65-75)^\circ\text{C}$, for three h, notice light brown participate, filter and wash twice with cold ethanol and acetone, after dry give 0.31 g, %75.5, M.P: (343-345) $^\circ\text{C}$, formula : $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{Co}$, M.wt :529.5 gm/mole, C:54.44, H:6.47, N:15.87, O: 12.09, Co: 11.13 found C:54.21, H:6.70, N:15.90, O:11.97, Co:10.99.

C. Synthesis of [Ni L] Complex

Add (1×10^{-3} mole, 0.24 gm) from $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dissolve in 10ml of ethanol to (0.001 mole, 0.473 g) H_2L dissolving on 10 ml of ethanol with stirring and reflux to $(65-75)^\circ\text{C}$ For three h, notice brown participate, after filter and washing in cold ethanol and acetone, after drying gave 0.31 g, %75.5, M.P: (300) $^\circ\text{C}$, formula : $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{Ni}$, M.wt : 529.3 gm/mole, C:54.46, H:6.48, N:15.88, O: 12.09, Ni:11.09 found C:54.70, H:6.77, N:15.00, O:11.88, Ni:11.20.

D. Synthesis of [Cu L] Complex

Add (1×10^{-3} , 1.34 gm) from $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dissolve in 10ml of ethanol to (0.001 mol, 0.473 g) H_2L dissolving on 10 ml of ethanol with stirring and reflux to $(65-75)^\circ\text{C}$, for three h, notice green participate, filtered and washing in cold ethanol and acetone,¹⁵ after drying gave 0.31 gm, %75.5, M.P: (185-187) $^\circ\text{C}$, formula : $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{Cu}$, M.wt :534.1 gm/mole, C:53.97, H:6.42, N:15.73, O:11.98, Cu:11.90 found C:54.13, H:6.59, N:16.01, O:12.11, Cu:11.79.

Fig.. 2. Synthesis of Complexes

V. FT-IR SPECTRA

FT-IR spectra chart for the ligand H_2L (potassium bromide disk) Fig.3 show bands belong to stretching vibration for $\nu(-\text{NH}_2)$ in 3201 cm^{-1} , amide $\nu(-\text{NH})$ 3105 cm^{-1} , aliphatic $\nu(-\text{CH}_2)$ in 2956 cm^{-1} , aromatic $\nu(\text{CH})$ 3055 cm^{-1} ¹⁴ strong band 1585 cm^{-1} for amide's carbonyl group. while $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ doesn't show due to inter hydrogen bonding, and FT-IR spectra for complexes Fig.4, Fig.5, Fig.6 and Fig.7 show different shift for $\nu(-\text{NH}_2)$ around $(3309-3385) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu(\text{NH})$ about $(3280-3180) \text{ cm}^{-1}$, aliphatic $\nu(-\text{CH}_2)$ in $(2829-2889) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ cm^{-1} and respectively that prove coordination. ¹⁵⁻¹⁷ table (1) show that.

Fig. 3. The infrared spectra for free H₂L ligand

Fig. 4. The infrared spectra for FeL

Fig. 5. The infrared spectra for CoL

Fig. 6. The infrared spectra for NiL

Fig. 7. The infrared spectra for CuL

TABLE.1FT.IR SPECTRA FOR LIGAND AND IT COMPLEXES

Comp.	ν (-NH ₂)	ν (N-H)	ν (C-H) aromatic	ν (C-H) aliphatic	ν (C-H)	ν (C=O)	ν (M-O)	ν (M-N)
C ₂₄ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₄	3201	3105	3055	2956	2879	1585
[C ₂₄ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₄ Fe]	3371	3280	3080	2951	2887	1529	560	448-418
[C ₂₄ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₄ Co]	3200	3180	3040	2958	2829	1583	572-530	449-422
[C ₂₄ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₄ Ni]	3313	3217	3005	2920	2889	1649	597	453-413
[C ₂₄ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₄ Cu]	3313	3238	3120	2945	2883	1566	543	470-445

VI. UV- VISIBLE SPECTRA

The absorption electronic transitions spectra of amide ligand and complexes has been recorded in (0.001) M Ethanol solvent at (25)°C . Fig.8 belong to ligand showed two transitions bands in (λ =209) nm (47847) cm⁻¹ for $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and (λ =290) nm (34483) cm⁻¹ for $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ respectively ¹⁸

Fig. 8. UV-Visb. Spectra for H₂L

The absorption electronic transitions spectra for complexes showed different bands , Fe (II) complex Fig.9 is light brown color show three Abs. bands at (λ = 204.5) nm (48899.8) cm⁻¹ , (λ = 269.5) nm (37105.8) cm⁻¹ due to charge transition ,in addition single band in visible region at (λ =908) nm (11013.2) cm⁻¹ assigned to transition type (⁵T_{2g} → ⁵E_{2g}) . belong to an octahedral shape for di valance Iron complex. The spectrum Fig.10 for di valance Co complex is brown color show two bands at (λ =275.5) nm (36297.6) cm⁻¹ belong to (C.T.) and another one at (λ = 469) nm (21321.7) cm⁻¹ belong to (⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}) transition for octahedral shape. ¹⁹ and complex of Ni(II) Fig.11 brown color showed two absorption bands at (λ =219.5) nm (45558.1) cm⁻¹ , (λ =275) nm (36363.6) cm⁻¹ assigned to a charge transfer and one in visible at (λ = 887.5) nm (11267.6) cm⁻¹ to (³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}) transition Due to octahedral shape, finally Cu(II) complex spectrum Fig.12 showed green color. exhibits two absorption bands at (λ = 229.5) nm (43573.0) cm⁻¹ identified for (C.T.) and (λ = 666.5) nm (15003.6) cm⁻¹ due to (²E_g → ²T_{2g}) transition show an octahedral structure for di valance copper complex.^{20,21}

Fig. 9. UV-Vis. Spectra for [FeL]

Fig. 10. UV-Vis. Spectra for [CoL]

Fig. 11. UV-Vis. Spectra for [NiL]

Fig. 12. UV-Vis. Spectra for [CuL]

Fig.15. inhibitory effect for H₂L and Complexes in E. Coli Bacteria

Fig.14. inhibitory effect for H₂L and in Staph.aureus bacteria

XI. CONCLUSION

The synthesis of poly dentate amide ligand done by condensation reaction between tyrosine amino acid and tri ethylene tetra amine, ligand and complexes were colored and stable in temp. and air, measurements like ¹H-NMR, UV-Vis, FT-IR, C.H.N and magnetic susceptibility supported octahedral structure for all prepared di valence (Nickel, Copper, Iron, Cobalt) complexes, while electric conductivity show the non- electrolytic property for all prepared complexes.

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